

Influence of Motivation on Academic Staff Morale and Productivity in University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State

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Abstract: This study aims to establish whether there exists a relationship between motivation and morale and productivity. Survey design was adopted as 217 academic staff was sampled using cross-sectional data from a semi-structured questionnaire. The result revealed that both monetary and non-monetary motivational incentives have a significant positive relationship with morale and productivity in the study institution. Specifically, it was revealed that there is a strong relationship between financial incentives and academic staff morale and productivity. ($\beta = .943$; $t = 27.207$; $P < .000$). Non-monetary incentives had positive influence on the level of academic staff morale and productivity ($\beta = .938$; $t = 26.165$; $p < .000$). Furthermore, it was revealed that incentives and rewards impact positively on academic staff morale and productivity ($\beta = .943$; $t = 27.207$; $P < .000$). We recommend that University management should be more strategic in implementing its yearly financial reward and non financial incentives as this will induce the employees to engage in work behaviour that drives higher-level of productivity.

Key words: *Moral and Productivity, Motivation, Monetary Incentive, Non-monetary Incentive*

Introduction

One of the most pressing issues facing organizations of all kinds, both public and

private, non-profit, and academic, is staff motivation. Most organizations, however,

struggle to identify what drives people and how to put those drives into practice in order to create the levels of motivation required to improve organizational performance (Jackson, 2010). In order to achieve this, management in any kind of organization must look inward to see how best to boost staff morale through various incentives and rewards. Programs for rewards and recognition are the most important aspect in maintaining enthusiastic and strong self-esteem among employees. According to Dickson (2001), one of a manager's responsibilities is to successfully inspire their staff and shape their behavior in order to increase organizational effectiveness. As a result, collaboration among all members of the system is essential to achieving goals. A vital resource for the success of a higher education institution is its academic staff. Particularly, academic personnel makes up a large portion of higher education institutions' budgets and is crucial to the achievement of the institution's goals. The quality of the higher education experience is largely determined by the performance of academic staff members in their roles as researchers, teachers, and managers. This has a big impact on student learning and, in turn, the contribution that these institutions can make to society. The majority of higher

education institutions, according to Bassey (2009), have an implicit or stated mission to provide all of their students with a high-quality educational experience. He believes that academic staff oversees this educational process and serves as the primary point of contact for pupils.

Thus, a key factor in judging this interface's quality is their motivation. According to Dessler (2003), a business runs the danger of losing important personnel and will find it more difficult to attract top talent if employee motivation and morale are not enhanced.

However, with the right assistance, highly driven academic staff members can establish a name for themselves and the institution in the fields of research, publishing, and professional development on a national and worldwide scale. The ability of the university to draw in top-notch students, research funding, and consulting jobs may be significantly impacted by such a profile. Incentives can be used to draw in new hires, keep key staff members, inspire workers, support the achievement of human resource goals, and gain a competitive edge (Bratton and Gold, 2007). According to Andrew (2004), the primary factors influencing employee motivation are incentives, rewards, and recognitions.

This is especially crucial in the very competitive academic environment where colleges and institutions are vying for top talent to enhance the caliber of instruction and build stellar reputations. According to Mullins (2005), increasing organizational productivity and performance requires more than just having a staff with the proper abilities and skills; instead, individual effort, motivation, and employee retention are crucial. As a result, a key factor in determining the success of a business is the performance of each individual employee or the workforce as a whole. Every published paper about teachers extols the roles and importance of teachers in the educational process, highlighting the essential and timely subject of academic staff motivational incentives at all levels of the education system. But those tasked with overseeing and managing teachers appear to turn elsewhere when it comes to finding ways to enhance and inspire them. Too long, issues regarding teachers' conditions have been taboo. The problem of teachers has been largely ignored in educational debates due to its sensitivity, yet the state of teachers' conditions has gotten intolerably bad. Nonetheless, the greatest single category of public servants is made up of teachers.

Regretfully, governments often view issues affecting teachers' morale, salaries, and other service conditions as unsolvable, even in the face of resource availability, despite the critical role teachers play in transforming society from an industrial to a technological and knowledge-based society. Because of these actions, the public now views academic staff members in the teaching service as "forgotten," deserving of little respect. This has also led to an uneasy scenario where academic staff members appear to hold a vacuous position in Nigerian society, and as a result, the society as a whole has continued to harbor mixed feelings regarding academic staff members. Given the aforementioned conflicting concerns, it is appropriate to use the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, to investigate the effect of motivation on academic staff morale and productivity. A literature review, a methodology part, an analysis and discussion section, and a conclusion make up the remaining portion of the paper.

Concept of Motivation

Motivation George (2018) argued that motivation is any influence that portrays, directs, or maintains people's goal-directed

behaviors. It speaks of the motivation that propels someone to behave in a particular manner. An individual's behavior is determined by an innate motivation. Motivation is defined as "those psychological characteristics of human beings that contribute to an individual's level of commitments to the organizational goals and objectives" by James and Stoner⁸ in another study. This very definition is even more important when we consider the importance of employee motivation on employee performance. Hemakumara (2020) expressed the view that motivation is a factor that induced an individual to expend effort towards achieving a particular task. The author further stated that a person's motivation is the determinant of that person's level of enthusiasm for specific behavioral patterns and is dependent on the ambition, needs, and wants of such individuals. Motivation could also be expressed in terms of the mental process that has the ability within the short and long run to decide the kind of actions a person takes when subjected to specific stimuli. Motivation could be seen as the psychological rationale within the employee that serves to induce the manifestation or expression of the negative and positive dynamics of frustration, fixation, anger,

withdrawal, team building, excitement by or within a particular employee (Raya; 2015). This is particularly important within the service delivery industry where customer demands are premium, and customers require a high level of service from the organization regardless of the various constraints on the system. It is argued in the literature that an individual's motivation is generally linked to motivational factors that surround them and the motivational factors are usually connected to incentives and rewards systems. The rewards system surrounding an individual can be self-afflicted/accomplishment targets or goals or others influenced. Again, such a collection of rewards and incentives is categorized into monetary and non-monetary. It is important to note that a review of the literature points that even though motivation is key to organizational performance and employee performance, it is not the only driving force to organizational performance. There are other factors influencing performance including skills, knowledge, feelings, emotions, and other inhibiting conditions which are often beyond the employee's sphere of control (Dereje; 2020). Riggio (2014) also pointed out that while the conventional view is to assume that the 'motivated worker is the productive worker',

it is also important to know that having a highly motivated workforce is one important factor contributing to employee productivity. This is because of the increasingly complex dynamics of the business environment in which a company must operate.

Non-monetary motivational factors

It is important to note that non-monetary motivational factors relate more to employee works environment and relationship between the employees and the organization. Reward systems are frequently designed with an employee's quality of life in mind, as they are seen to have a more profound and long-lasting impact on them (Nwannebuife, 2017). Non-monetary motivators focus on the long-term aspirations of the individual and integrate those goals with the organization's goals, going beyond the immediate rewards. According to Deci and Ryan (2010), an organization's relationship with its employees is where non-monetary motivation originates. It touches on a number of topics, including the work ethics, regulations, internal disciplinary procedure, and interpersonal relationships. For example, Mokhniuk and Yushchyshyna (2018) found that the following non-financial motivating factors—such as getting verbal or written acknowledgment, getting more days off,

having a competitive work environment, and having job-related autonomy—are crucial to employee performance. A few more are showing gratitude in public, expanding or improving one's career, getting on- or off-the-job training, and having a strong sense of teamwork.

Monetary motivational factors

Financial motivational elements, such as salary, financial incentives, and wages, are closely associated with monetary motivational factors (Armstrong, 2009). Finance has always been a major factor in determining an employee's life and effectiveness within any given company (Giancola, 2014). According to Deci and Ryan (2010), money plays a major role in employee motivation, but how valuable we think it is depends on how much we value social norms, reciprocity and justice, trust, and reliability. When it comes to financial incentives for performance, the outcomes will also be significantly influenced by the caliber of the performance metrics, the kind of task being rewarded, and the award itself. Monetary motivation is frequently hard to maintain for an extended length of time without reevaluation and adjustment based on the organization performance and status of the economy, in contrast to non-monetary

motivation, which concentrates on the relationship between the business and its employees as well as within the employee. The explanation is that employee motivation varies with time, and an organization needs to adapt to comprehend these changes in order to inspire employees to achieve greater productivity. Monetary motivational behaviors, in stark contrast to non-monetary motivation, are external to the task or activity under review. The idea that financial incentives at work, such as pay, benefits, and opportunities for promotion, are set by the company that employee works for and are therefore externally imposed on them. Pritchard (2016) added that financial considerations are intended to be made in order for workers to receive societal or large benefits. Therefore, the argument goes that individual employees whose primary source of incentive is money will only remain motivated as long as money is available.

Employee Productivity

Productivity in the context of economics is defined as the ratio of output to input. It is a measurement of the effectiveness of manufacturing over a specific time frame. Productivity to an engineer refers to new machinery, controls, measurement, and technologies. Productivity can signify

different things to different business managers, such as effectiveness and efficiency. This is due to the lack of quantifiable output units, a productivity function, and an efficient data base in management. Productivity is defined by Agoro (1991) as the output per unit of factor input over a specified time period. It represents the proportion of money generated to resources used throughout the production process. Adekoya (1991) concurs, highlighting the fact that productivity is a gauge of how well labor resources and abilities are assembled inside an organization and applied to achieving a predetermined outcome. The ratio of input to output is a common way to quantify manufacturing efficiency. Getting the best performance out of workers while spending the least amount of money on labor wages is the key to an organization's efficient use of labor. Productivity, according to Prokopenko (1992), is the result of the effective and efficient use of all available resources, including capital, labor, materials, energy, information, and time. This definition was provided by the International Labour Organization (ILO). Nwasike's (1991) term serves as a working definition in this study. "The efficiency with which inputs are used

to produce the desired output" is how she defined productivity.

According to Udo-Aka (2009), productivity is a gauge of an organization's total performance, efficacy, and production efficiency. "The measure of how well a nation's resources are utilized for accomplishing a set of results...reaching the highest level of performance with the least expenditure of resources" is what Akerele (1991, 50) claims productivity is. It is evident from the foregoing that the productivity notion is still relevant and essential to human existence, and that it may be applied to all areas of human endeavor. Productivity is defined in this study as effectiveness, efficiency, performance, and growth. According to Prokopenko (2006), "productivity improvement is not just doing things better." It is performing the proper tasks more effectively. Therefore, increasing productivity depends on how well the key socio-production system components that affect productivity are recognized and applied. According to Nworah (1991), productivity improvement is the rise in output (goods and services) obtained from a

given input through improved resource management and utilization, including human resources. It's not always about making them operate more efficiently. When productivity increases, work is typically easier.

Theoretical Framework

Theoretical framework of the study is based on the expectancy theory propounded by H. Vroom. Vroom (1992), in his expectancy theory asserts that the strength of rewards impact on workers' motivation and effort are functions of three factors: expectancy, instrumentality, and valence. Expectancy is the workers perception of the strength of the link between effort and performance.

Luneneburg (2011) highlights on Vroom expectancy theory is based on the three key elements; expectancy, instrumentality, and valence. According to him, a person is motivated to the degree that he or she believes that (a) effort will lead to acceptable performance (expectancy), (b) performance will be rewarded (instrumentality), and (c) the value of the rewards is highly positive (valence).

Figure 1 Basic Expectancy Model (Adapted from Luneneburg, 2011).

Empirical Review

George (2018) conducted an extensive literature review on the influence of employee motivation on employee performance using an exploratory research approach. The researcher agrees that motivated employees perform better than unmotivated employees in the organization. The researcher concludes that a stressed and depressed heart is negative to the working environment and organization performance whereas a motivated employee brings positive energy in the work environment leading to higher organization performance. Elvina and Chao (2019) on the nexus between employee motivation and work performance using the employees of VTB Bank of Russia as a case study. The study used a quantitative research design collect relevant data and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used to test the two hypotheses. Findings revealed that the employees of VTB Bank valued both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation for their industrial performance. However, extrinsic

motivation had stronger positive relationship with employees' performance. Following this, the study strongly challenged the employers to improve the payment policies and procedures capable of drawing attention, encouraging, retaining, and satisfying workers in the workplace. The study argued that motivation either extrinsic or intrinsic impacts employee performance, but one would wonder how the author came about that conclusion since they used correlation is establishing a relationship which is not an impact analysis.

Lorincova et al. (2019) focused more on employee motivation as a tool to achieve sustainability of business processes. The study aimed to investigate and establish the main disparities in the perception of the desired level of motivation, particularly with respect to gender and job category. The study also showed that motivational factors, such as basic salary, workplace atmosphere and good teamwork, greatly motivated all the workers. The researchers advanced the implementation of the results in

motivational programs by the employees within the human resource department to enhance effective human resource management. There are also studies which rather focused on organization performance rather than employee performance.

Ojogbo et al. (2018) conducted research to establish the implications of employee motivation on organizational performance in the Nigerian media industry. The research aimed to determine the factors put in place to motivate employees in the Delta State Broadcasting Service to improve their performance. The study employed a mixed (quantitative and qualitative) methodology was adopted, and the data were collected through questionnaires and interviews.

Research Methods

This study adopts a survey research design. Specifically, the study sampled academic staff of University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Umuagwo Imo State . The available population revealed that there were two hundred and seventeen (217) academic staff of the university. Taro Yamani sample size determination formular was engaged to arrive at a sample of one hundred and four (104) academic staffs who

were randomly selected through simple random sampling technique. A five-point Likert scale instrument was designed and distributed to the respondents and were returned to the researcher. Validity and reliability of research instrument was ascertained by a pilot study using 10 employees of the institution. Their feedback was primarily used to make modifications to the final questionnaire used in generating data. Similarly, Cronbach Alfa was conducted on the pilot study data with an average of 0.89% which previous literature considered sufficient (Austin and Adebayo; 2021; Ridwan and Joseph; 2021). The study was analyzed using a combination of descriptive statistics of means, standard deviation, and frequencies alongside inferential statistics such as simple linear regression to determine the impact of motivation on academic staff morale and productivities

Research Findings and Discussions

From the table above, it can be seen that out of the 104 questionnaires distributed, 95 or (91.35%) were correctly filled and returned while 9 or (8.65%) questionnaires were not returned

Table 1 Questionnaire Distribution And Return Rate

S/No	Question	Response	No	%
	Questionnaire return rate	Distributed	104	100
		Returned	95	91.35
		Not Returned	9	8.65
Total			104	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 shows the questionnaire distribution and return rate from the respondents. Out of the 104 questionnaires distributed, 95

representing (91.35%) was successfully filled and returned while 9 were not returned representing (8.65%).

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents by Age Range

Question	Response (yrs)	No	%
Age range of respondents	20-25	11	11.58
	26-35	39	41.05
	36-45	29	30.53
	46 and above	16	16.84
Total		95	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 shows that out of the 95 respondents surveyed, 11 or (11.58%) of the respondents are within the age of 20-25, 39 or (41.05%) are within the ages of 26-35yrs, 29 or

(30.53%) of the respondents are within the ages of 36-45yrs while 16 or (16.84%) are within the age of 46 and above.

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents by Gender

S/No	Question	Response	No	%
	Sex	Male	59	62.11
		Female	36	37.89
Total			95	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3 indicates that out of the 95 respondents used in this study, 59 (62.11%)

are Male while 36 (37.89%) are female.

Table 4 Distribution of Respondents by Marital Status

S/No	Question	Response	No	%
	Marital Status	Married	42	44.21
		Single	53	55.79
Total			95	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

It can be seen from table 4 that 42 or (44.21%) of the respondents are married while 53 or (55.79%) of the respondents are still single

Table 5 Distribution of Respondents by Educational qualification

S/No	Question	Response	No	%
	Educational Qualifications	Ph.D	66	69.47
		M.Sc	29	30.53
Total			95	100

Source: Field Survey 2023

From the Table 5 above, it shows that 66 or (69.47%) of the respondents hold Ph.D. Degree while 29 or (30.53%) of the respondents hold M. Sc degree.

Questionnaire Responses by Respondents

Table 6 Impact of rewards and incentives on academic staff morale and productivity responses

Rewards and Incentives Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Freq.	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq.	%
impact of rewards 1	35	36.8	48	50.5	5	5.3	4	4.2	3	3.2
impact of rewards 2	47	49.5	33	34.7	3	3.2	3	3.2	9	9.5
impact of rewards 3	28	29.5	53	55.5	2	2.1	5	5.3	7	7.4
impact of rewards 4	32	33.7	44	46.3	5	5.3	10	10.5	4	4.2

Table 6 shows that 3 (3.2%) strongly disagree; 4 (4.2%) disagree; 5 (5.3%) are undecided; 48 (50.5%) agree while 35(36.8%) strongly agree that Competence need satisfaction influence productivity On Autonomy need satisfaction encourage satisfaction 9 (9.5%) strongly disagree, 3 (3.2%) disagree, 3 (3.2%) were undecided,

33 (34.7%) agree, while 47 (49.5%) strongly agree. On Supervisors' performance ratings boost my work commitment, 7 (7.4%) strongly disagree, 5(5.3%) disagree, 2(2.1%) were undecided, 53 (55.5%) agree, while 28 (29.5%) strongly agree. Again, on monitory awards encourage dedication, 32 (33.7%) and 44 (46.3%) respondents strongly agreed

and agree on the statement respectively. while 5(5.3%) were indecisive, however, 10

(10.5%) and 4(4.2%) disagreed with the assertion.

Table 7 Determination of the association between financial incentives and academic staff morale and productivity responses

Workplace Safety Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
financial incentives 1	54	56.8	32	33.7	2	2.1	4	4.2	3	3.2
financial incentives 2	55	57.9	27	28.4	6	6.3	5	5.3	2	2.1
financial incentives 3	42	44.2	31	32.6	7	7.4	10	10.5	5	5.3
financial incentives 4	29	30.5	33	34.7	6	6.3	16	16.8	11	11.6

Table 7 indicates that 54 (56.8%) and 32 (33.7%) respondents strongly agreed and agree on All types of short-term bonuses (cash, family meal vouchers, and verbal rewards) increased performance but 2 (2.1%) were neutral while 4(4.2%) and 3 (3.2%) totally disagree with the statement. However, 55 (57.9%) and 27 (28.4%) respondents supported the statement on the adoption of a pay-for-performance programme by professional organisations results in higher levels of performance among the participating professionals. 6 (6.3%) were indifference while 5 (5.3%) and 2(2.1%) respondents did

not agree with the statement. On Goal-based pay-for-performance bonus plans lower goals but increase goal accuracy when participative goal-setting is applied, while 42 (44.2%) and 31 (32.6%) agreed 10 (10.5%) and 5 (5.3%) disagreed on the statement and 7 (7.4%) was indifference. On The effect of monetary incentives on job effort is stronger for civil servants with higher levels of extrinsic motivation at the baseline, 11 (11.6%) strongly disagree, 16(16.8%) disagree, 6 (6.3%) were undecided, 33 (34.7%) agree, while 29 (30.5%) strongly agree.

Table 8 Examination of the extent to which non monetary incentive impacts on academic staff morale and productivity responses.

Organizational Climate Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Non monetary incentive 1	32	33.7	43	45.3	8	8.4	5	5.3	7	7.4
Non monetary incentive 2	37	38.9	29	30.5	10	10.5	11	11.6	8	8.4
Non monetary incentive 3	39	41.1	42	44.2	5	5.3	5	5.3	4	4.2
Non monetary incentive 4	41	43.2	33	34.7	8	8.4	4	4.2	9	9.5

Table 8 shows that respondents strongly agree and agree on if I see a chance of something I want, I move on it right away 32 (33.7%) and 43 (45.3%) respectively while 5 (5.3%), 7 (7.4%) respondents disagree with the statement, 8 (8.4%) respondents were indifferent. Again, 37 (38.9%) and 29 (30.5%) respondents agreed on When I'm doing well at something, I love to keep at it.

10(10.5%) were indecisive, however, 11(11.6%) and 8 (8.4%) disagreed with the assertion. On when I see an opportunity for something I like, I get excited right away, 39 (41.1%) and 42 (44.2%) respondents agreed respectively while 5(5.3%) and 4(9.5%) respondents did not support the statement but 5(5.3%) respondents were neutral. Furthermore, on when I go after something I use a "no holds barred" approach, while 41 (43.2%) and 33 (34.7%) agreed on the statement 4(4.2%) and 9(9.5%) disagreed and 8(8.4%) were indifference.

Table 9 Academic staff morale and productivity responses.

Employee Items	Efficiency		Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Disagree		Strongly Disagree	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
morale and productivity1	45	47.4	38	40.0	4	4.2	5	5.3	3	3.2		
morale and productivity2	53	55.8	28	29.5	5	5.3	2	2.1	7	7.4		
morale and productivity3	44	46.3	32	33.7	4	4.2	5	5.3	10	10.5		

Table 9 shows that respondents 45 (47.4%) and 38 (40.0%) respectively supported the statement that results of the work done

provide satisfaction for the organization and the community while 5 (5.3%) and 3 (3.2%) disprove with the statement but 4 (4.2%) respondents were indifferent. Secondly 53

(55.8%) and 28 (29.5%) respondents agreed that Work performed in accordance with work standards and guidelines influence productivity

while 2 (2.1%) and 7 (7.4%) did not agree with the statement, however, 5 (5.3%) respondent were indifferent. The implementation of the work in accordance with the time and conditions set influence productivity was strongly supported by 44

(46.3%) and 32 (33.7%) respondent respectively while 5 (5.3%) and 10 (10.5%) did not support it, but 4 (4.2%) respondents were neutral.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One:

Ho₁: Rewards and incentives have no significant relationship with academic staff morale and productivity

Table 10a Output of the Regression Analyses for Hypotheses One
Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.943 ^a	.888	.887	.33031	.393

a. Predictors: (Constant), Rewards and incentives

b. Dependent Variable: Morales and productivity

The Model Summary in Table 10a indicates that R .943 i.e. simple correlation value representing the correlation between the actual scores of the dependent variable and the scores for the dependent variable predicted by the regression equation, the R squared .888 (which is simple squared correlation value that if multiplied by 100

can be understand as a percentage to indicate that the independent variables account for 88.8% of the variance in the scores of the dependent variable), the Adjusted R square .887 and the Standard Error of the Estimate .33031. The Durbin Watson is .393 which indicates that the data has no redundant variable.

Table 10b ANOVA^a Output of the Regression Analyses for Hypotheses One
ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Model
1	Regression	80.759	1	80.759	740.195	.000 ^b
	Residual	10.147	93	.109		
	Total	90.905	94			

a. Dependent Variable: Morales and productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Rewards and incentives

Table 10b is the ANOVA output from regression analysis which has a F score of 740.195 and is highly statistical significant at .000 below the .01 margin of

error. This implies that the model was a good fit and that the coefficient of simple correlations R is significantly different from zero.

Table 10c Output of the Regression Analyses for Hypotheses One
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.089	.076		-1.173	.244
	(Constant)	.997	.037	.943	27.207	.000
	Rewards and incentives	-.089	.076		-1.173	.244

a. Dependent Variable: Morale and productivity

Table 10c the output from regression analysis show that coefficients has significant relationship and the hypotheses should be accepted in the alternate form.

Rewards and incentives was found to have significance relationship with morale and productivity of academic staff ($\beta = .943$; $t = 27.207$; $P < .000$)

Hypothesis Two:

Ho₂: Financial incentives has no positive significant influence on academic staff morale and productivity.

Table 11a Output of the Regression Analyses for Hypotheses Two
Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.910 ^a	.827	.826	.45025	.435

a. Predictors: (Constant), Financial incentives

b. Dependent Variable: morale and productivity

The Model Summary in Table 11a indicate that R .910 i.e. simple correlation value representing the correlation between the actual scores of the dependent variable and the scores for the dependent variable predicted by the regression equation, the R squared . 827 (which is simple squared correlation value that if multiplied by 100

can be understand as a percentage to indicate that the independent variables account for 82.7% of the variance in the scores of the dependent variable), the Adjusted R square . 826 and the Standard Error of the Estimate .45025. The Durbin Watson is .435 which indicates that the data has no redundant variable.

Table 11b ANOVA^a Output of the Regression Analyses for Hypotheses Two
ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Model
1	Regression	90.367	1	90.367	445.754	.000 ^b
	Residual	18.854	93	.203		
	Total	109.221	94			

a. Dependent Variable: morale and productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant), financial incentive

Table 11b, the ANOVA output of the regression analysis which has F score of 445.754 and is highly statistical significant at .000 below the .01 margin of error. This implies

that the model was a good fit and that the coefficient of simple correlations R is significantly different from zero.

Table 11c Output of the Regression Analyses for Hypotheses Two
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.192	.092		2.091	.039
	Financial incentives	1.024	.049	.910	21.113	.000

a. Dependent Variable: morale and productivity

Table 11c, the output from regression analysis indicates that the coefficients have significant relationship and the hypotheses should be accepted in the alternate form. Financial

incentives was found to have significance relationship with morale and productivity of academic staff ($\beta = .910$; $t = 21.113$; $P < .000$)

Hypothesis Three:

H₀₃: Non monetary incentive has no significant relationship with academic staff morale and productivity.

Table 12a Output of the Regression Analyses for Hypotheses Three
Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.938 ^a	.880	.879	.45486	.448

a. Predictors: (Constant), non monetary incentives

b. Dependent Variable: morale and productivity

The Model Summary in Table 12a indicate that R .938 i.e. simple correlation value representing the correlation between the actual scores of the dependent variable and the scores for the dependent variable predicted by the regression equation, the R squared . 880 (which is simple squared correlation value that if multiplied by 100

can be understand as a percentage to indicate that the independent variables account for 88.0% of the variance in the scores of the dependent variable), the Adjusted R square . 879 and the Standard Error of the Estimate. 45486. The Durbin Watson is .448 which indicates that the data has no redundant variable.

Table 12b ANOVA^a Output of the Regression Analyses for Hypotheses Three
ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Model
1	Regression	141.643	1	141.643	684.620	.000 ^b
	Residual	19.241	93	.207		
	Total	160.884	94			

- a. Dependent Variable: moral and productivity
- b. Predictors: (Constant), non monetary incentive

Table 12b indicate that ANOVA from the regression analysis indicate that F score is 684.620 and is highly statistical significant at .000 below the .01 margin of error. This

implies that the model was a good fit and that the coefficient of simple correlations R is significantly different from zero.

Table 12c Output of the Regression Analyses for Hypotheses Three
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.096	.097		.991	.324
	Non monetary incentives	1.075	.041	.938	26.165	.000

- a. Dependent Variable: morale and productivity

Table 12c the coefficients show a significant relationship and the hypothesis should be accepted in the alternate form non monetary incentive was found to have significance relationship with moral and productivity of academic staff ($\beta = .938$; $t = 26.165$; $p < .000$)

Discussion

The SPSS output as shown in the table above indicates that rewards and incentives has significant relationship with academic staff morale and productivity ($\beta = .943$; $t = 27.207$; $P < .000$). The relationship that exists between rewards and incentives and

academic staff morale and productivity is shown to be significant at 0.000 significant levels. Based on these guidelines the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternate hypothesis. Hence the alternate hypothesis was accepted. Meaning there is a significant relationship between rewards and incentives and academic staff morale and productivity. This is an indication that rewards and incentives impact positively on academic staff morale and productivity. However, the finding of the study re-enacts the previous research findings of Guzzo, Zette, and Katzell (2000) that incentives had effect on productivity of employees. The finding of the study also provides support for the assertion of Dematteo, Eby and Sundstrom (1998) that reward compensation is a utilization of pay system through which efforts of various subunits and individuals are directed towards the achievement of organization's objectives.

The result in the table above indicates that financial incentive has statistical relationship with academic staff morale and productivity ($\beta = .910$; $t = 21.113$; $P < .000$). The relationship that exists between financial incentive and academic staff morale and productivity is shown to be significant at 0.000 significant levels. Based on these guidelines the researchers rejected the null hypothesis and uphold the alternate hypothesis. Hence the alternate hypothesis was accepted. Meaning there is a significant relationship between financial incentives and academic staff morale and productivity. Thus, there is a strong relationship between financial incentives and academic staff morale and productivity. The finding of the

study lends credence to the theoretical foundation of Vroom's (1964) expectancy theory which postulates a clear link between effort and financial incentive that ultimately influence work behaviour of employees.

The result in the table above indicates that non monetary incentives have significant relationship with the academic staff morale and productivity ($\beta = .938$; $t = 26.165$; $p < .000$). The relationship that exists between non monetary incentives and academic staff morale and productivity is proven to be significant at 0.00 significant levels. It is therefore safe to imply that non monetary incentives have significant relationship with academic staff morale and productivity. Thus, non-monetary incentive had a significant positive effect on academic staff morale and productivity and the hypothesis is accepted in alternate form. The finding of the study is affirmation of the theoretical postulate of Herzberg, and Snyderman (1957) Two-Factor model of non-monetary reward as motivators of employee behaviour for better performance.

Summary of Findings

Based on the analysis on the influence of motivations on academic staff morale and productivity in University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Umuagwo Imo State the following findings emerged:

1. Incentives and rewards impact positively on academic staff morale and productivity in University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Umuagwo Imo State ($\beta = .943$; $t = 27.207$; $P < .000$).
2. There is a strong relationship between financial incentives and academic staff

morale and productivity. ($\beta = .943$; $t = 27.207$; $P < .000$).

3. Non-monetary incentives had positive influence on the level of academic staff morale and productivity in University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Umuagwo Imo State ($\beta = .938$; $t = 26.165$; $p < .000$)

Conclusion

This study aimed at examining influence of motivation on academic staff morale and productivity in University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Umuagwo Imo State. It observes that the academic staff of the University place great value on different motivations given to them and this boosts their morale and productivity. It therefore concludes that academic staff place great value on the different incentives and rewards given to them by their employers. Hence, when these incentive and rewards are not

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given, academic staff tends to express displeasure through poor performance and non-commitment to their jobs.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were provided:

1. Incentives and rewards like bonuses, performance based rewards, should be provided to attract, retain and motivate academic staff to boost their performance and productivity.
2. Non-monetary rewards like autonomy, recognition, and praise should be offered to academic staff to promote staff retention, loyalty, industrial harmony, and performance.
3. Reward preferences of academic staff should be considered in the distribution of reward types to deserving academic staff for maximum performance.

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